

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6326620>

NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Jumaboyeva Noila Vahobjon qizi

*Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages,
Faculty II Foreign Language and Literature, a student.*

Annotation: *This article deals with the problem of finding new techniques and ways to increase motivation for learning foreign languages. One of these forms is new pedagogical technologies, the introduction of which contributes to the effective learning of the language.*

Key words: *new information technologies, pedagogical technology, independent work, linguistic social networks.*

In recent years, great changes have taken place in teacher education, which cover almost all aspects of the educational process. Increasingly, the question of the use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching foreign languages is being raised. New methods and forms of teaching are emerging, which, in turn, represent not only various technologies for the means of exchanging and transmitting information through which the educational process is carried out, but also one large system of teaching methods aimed at developing the communicative knowledge of students, improving speech skills. The main task of a foreign language is to teach practical mastery of a foreign language. The search for new pedagogical technologies is associated with a lack of motivation among students to learn a foreign language. The use of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages allows you to reproduce learning situations, helps to complement traditional teaching methods, contributes to the formation of fundamental skills of foreign language communication from the realization of the possibility of expressing thoughts in another language to the independent solution of communication problems, increases the desire, interest of students in learning, makes them - take a fresh look at the subjects being studied, thus revealing their creative and intellectual capabilities, talents. The main source of knowledge is electronic, educational Internet content, technological operations are to provide feedback from teachers and students, the exchange of knowledge between them. Smart education is a concept that involves a comprehensive modernization of all educational processes, as well as the methods and technologies used in these processes. Considering the current, innovative

technologies, one should dwell in more detail on the topic of using Internet resources in teaching a foreign language. With the help of web resources, you can perform the following tasks:

- include network materials in the content of the lesson;
- carry out an independent search for information by students as part of the work on the project;
- to organize and develop reading skills using materials from the network of any complexity;
- improve listening skills based on audio texts from a network of online resources;
- replenish the vocabulary with vocabulary, abbreviations of the modern foreign language;
- study the culture of a particular language.

At the moment, there are a large number of sites dedicated to the independent study of foreign languages. On such sites you can find ready-made lessons of foreign language teachers, exercises, audio recordings, grammatical explanations that are incomprehensible to the student. Thus, at present it is impossible to imagine the educational process without the use of innovative pedagogical technologies. Such technologies are firmly established in the modern education system. Today, a foreign language teacher has a lot of opportunities, which helps to conduct their classes more interesting, more informative. These opportunities encourage students to be more active. Compared with the traditional method of teaching, new implementations in teaching inevitably change the role of the teacher. Its task is to increase the independent work of students, support in the development of the individual. Such training allows you to increase motivation for learning, significantly increases interest in learning, and also gives good results in the formation of communication skills compared to the traditional method.

Prospects for the development of education are due to both the use of innovative methods and technologies in the meaningfulness of the educational process, and the growth of the teacher’s professional competence. In psychological and pedagogical research, the issue of forming a professionally competent working specialist in any area of modern production has become particularly relevant. Great importance can be assigned to a communication process, in the implementation of one of the important functional properties of professional competence, namely, the one that integrates development of creative abilities, so ingenious communication it takes place both internally and at the intercultural level, implying the usage of a foreign language.

LITERATURE:

1. Nazarova N. B., Mokhova O. L. New information technologies in teaching foreign languages // Modern problems of science and education. 2016. No. 3.
2. Application of SMART technologies in the educational process "Education without borders". MBOU "Secondary School No. 1". 2015. 20 p. [Electronic resource]. <https://infourok.ru/primenenie-smarttehnologii-v-obrazovatelnom-processe-mobu-soshobrazovanie-bez-granic-540134.html>
3. Sargsyan A. V. Use of Internet resources in a foreign language lesson [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://nsportal.ru/shkola/inostrannye42-yazyki/library/2016/02/23/ispolzovanie-internet-resursov-na-uroke-inostrannogo4>